

Bimodal Spectrum for the Curvature Fluctuations of Bilayer Vesicles: Pure Bending plus Hybrid Curvature-Dilation Modes

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(Received 10 October 2008; published 25 March 2009)

Abstract

We study thermal undulations of giant bilayer vesicles by flickering spectroscopy. The experimental fluctuation spectra are scrutinized in view of the classical Helfrich theory. Pure bending modes are revealed to be unable to predict the large fluctuations systematically found at a high wave vector. Hybrid curvature-dilational modes are then invoked as a more efficient mode of motion in producing high curvatures. A bimodal spectrum of the thermal undulations has been theoretically developed for the shelllike topology. Reconciliation between experiments and theory is achieved when this bimodal spectrum is considered.

DOI: 10.1103/PhysRevLett.102.128101

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The standard Helfrich treatment of the fluctuating single membrane leads to a spectrum of the thermal curvature fluctuations governed by surface tension and bending forces [1]. This model treats the deformable flat membrane as a single incompressible sheet with a constant thickness h . In the limit of small deformations ($\zeta < h$), the timeaveraged amplitude of the normal displacements of the membrane ζ_q is expected to decay with the wave number q as [2]:

$$P(q) = \langle \zeta_q \zeta_q \rangle = \frac{k_B T}{\gamma q^2 + \kappa q^4}, \quad (1)$$

where γ is the interfacial tension and κ the bending rigidity of the membrane. For large fluctuations, $q < q_{\text{cap}} \approx (\gamma/\kappa)^{1/2}$, curvature implies significant area increase thus resulting in a capillary regime driven by surface tension, $P_{\text{cap}}(q) \approx k_B T / \gamma q^2$. Conversely, small fluctuations involve high curvatures ($C \approx -\nabla^2 \zeta_q \sim q^2 \zeta_q$); thus, high- q shaped fluctuations are dominated by the resistance of the membrane to bending, i.e., at $q > q_{\text{cap}}$, $P_{\text{bend}}(q) \approx k_B T / \kappa q^4$. Dynamically, curvature undulations are expected to evolve as $\zeta_q(t) \sim \exp(-\Gamma_{\text{bend}} t)$ with a relaxation rate $\Gamma_{\text{bend}} \approx \kappa q^3 / 4\eta$ resulting from the hydrodynamic balance between the elastic inertia of the membrane and the viscous dissipation of the surrounding fluid (with bulk viscosity η) [3,4]. These physical grounds have been broadly exploited to study the bending elasticity in microemulsion droplets [5] and vesicles [6-8].

Helfrich's description formally corresponds to a planar sheet with free edges; thus, no lateral compression deformations are drawn upon small bending [9]. However, flexible membranes in a shell topology, e.g., bilayer lipid vesicles, represent a different elastic problem where curvature deformations necessarily imply a dilation of the membrane. Specifically, for a shell of radius R , both modes of deformation are first-order coupled, i.e. $\rho \sim \zeta / R$ [9];

thus, dilational effects might become significant even at small bending. Furthermore, bilayer membranes consist of a pair of compressible monolayers bound together, thus supporting lateral compression elasticity as well. The bilayer structure implies indeed that bending necessarily leads to a stretching of one of the monolayers and a compression of the other [9,10]. This fact has been recognized as being crucial to the understanding of the energetics [11] and the dynamics of conformational changes of lipid bilayer membranes [12,13].

Following the idea put forward by Evans and Young [12,14], Seifert and co-workers have postulated hybrid curvature modes, for which bending is coupled to dilational motion, as an alternative class, other than pure bending modes, for producing curvature motion in planar bilayer membranes [15,16]. Intrinsically, this class of motion engenders a difference in the lipid concentration of each monolayer, which consequently flow at a different velocity; this is because hybrid modes mainly dissipate energy through frictional sliding between both monolayers. In Seifert's theory bending and dilational fluctuations are dynamically coupled, giving rise to a dispersion relation characterized by a mixing between two viscous modes, the conventional pure bending mode and the hybrid one [15]. Monolayer dilational elasticity emerges then as the driving force

for lateral mass redistribution, which could become dominant over small distances. Indeed, creating a hybrid curvature mode above a crossover wave vector $q_C = (h\varepsilon/R\kappa)^{1/2}$ involves a work $F_{\text{hyb}} = \frac{1}{2}\varepsilon h q^2 \zeta_q \rho_q \approx \frac{1}{2}\varepsilon(h/R)q^2 \zeta_q \zeta_q$ [15], which is smaller than the energy of the pure bending one, i.e., $F_{\text{bend}} = \frac{1}{2}\kappa q^4 \zeta_q \zeta_q$ [2]. This crossover separates two regimes characterized by a different mixing between the two modes of motion. At $q \ll q_C$ the bending mode is found to be dominant with an amplitude determined by the bending rigidity $\langle \zeta_q \zeta_q \rangle \approx k_B T / \kappa q^4$, and a relaxation rate controlled by bulk friction, $\Gamma_{\text{bend}} \approx \kappa q^3 / 4\eta$. A secondary hybrid curvature-dilation mode is also found in this regime relaxing at a higher rate $\Gamma_{\text{frict}} = \varepsilon q^2 / 2b$ [15]. Conversely, at $q \gg q_C$ hybrid curvature-dilation modes with amplitude $\langle \zeta_q \rho_q \rangle \approx (6/h)(k_B T / \varepsilon q^2)$ become dominant, while the bending motion, now energetically more expensive than dilation, is found relaxing faster than the hybrid mode [15].

Giant unilamellar vesicles (GUVs) as prepared by the electroformation method [17] have been used over years as models of curved, near-spherical, bilayer membranes [18]. The mechanics of quasispherical GUVs can be studied in flickering experiments where the thermal fluctuations of the vesicle radius $\delta R (= \zeta)$ are recorded at the equatorial plane by fast video-microscopy [19]. In our setup fluctuating GUVs (sized typically $R \sim 20 \mu\text{m}$) are visualized in the phase-contrast mode by an inverted microscope (Nikon Eclipse TE2000, objective oil immersion $60\times$). The flickering dynamics is recorded by a cooled CCD (Nikon DS1QM, 14fps, 1Mpixel). The equatorial fluctuations $\delta R(x, t)$ are expanded in a series of discrete Fourier modes $\delta R = \sum_q \zeta_q \exp[iq_x^{(n)}x]$ where $q_x^{(n)} = n/R (n = 1, 2, \dots)$ are harmonics of the fundamental oscillation, i.e., $q_x^{(1)} = 2\pi/(2\pi R) = 1/R$, thus $q_x^{(n)} = nq_x^{(1)} = n/R$. The mechanical parameters are obtained by fitting the experimental mode amplitudes $\langle \zeta_q^2 \rangle$ to the theoretical spectrum particularized to the equatorial contour, $P_x(q_x)$. Since $\mathbf{q} = (q_x, q_y)$, its modulus is $q^2 = q_x^2 + q_y^2$; thus, for pure capillary motion the integrated equatorial spectrum vary as $P_{\text{cap}}(q_x) \approx (k_B T / \gamma) \int (q_x^2 + q_y^2)^{-1} dq_y \approx k_B T / \gamma q_x \sim q_x^{-1}$ and as $P_{\text{bend}}(q_x) \approx (k_B T / \kappa) \int (q_x^2 + q_y^2)^{-2} dq_y \approx k_B T / \kappa q_x^3 \sim q_x^{-3}$ for pure bending motion. At high q , the experimental fluctuation amplitudes are biased by two systematic instrumental contributions arising (a) from the finite integration time of the camera [19] and (b) from the finite spatial resolution of the images which produces background noise (pixelation) contributing systematically to the observed fluctuations [20]. Following Ref. [19], corrections due to both effects have been explicitly considered in our data analysis (see Sec. II in the auxiliary material [21]).

Figure 1 shows a typical experimental spectrum obtained for the equatorial undulations of fluid bilayer GUVs made of palmitoyl-oleyl-sn-glycero-phosphatidylcholine (POPC). For these vesicles the Helfrich theoretical spectrum fits well experimental data up to ca. 15th mode whose amplitudes are largely above the resolution limit. This is the spectral range typically exploited in the literature [19]. Here, the experimental spectra usually display a powerlike dependence $P_x \sim q_x^{-n}$ with $n \sim 2 - 2.6$, value intermediate between capillary and bending behaviors. For POPC vesicles one finds $\gamma \approx 10^{-8} \text{ J/m}^2$

and $\kappa \approx 4.0 \times 10^{-20}$ J $\approx 10k_B T$, in good agreement with literature data [18, 19]. From these parameters, the limit capillarylike behavior ($\sim q_x^{-1}$) might be only raised at wave vectors well below crossover at $q_{\text{cap}} \sim 5 \times 10^5$ m $^{-1}$, probably in the regime where undulation modes cannot develop larger [22]. On the other side, pure-bending-like behavior ($\sim q_x^{-3}$) is expected at $q > q_{\text{cap}}$. However, at high q , the tails of the experimental spectra are observed to systematically deviate up from the expected q^{-3} law; i.e., the curvature fluctuations are observed larger than those predicted by the pure bending spectrum. This feature, although at close proximity to the resolution limits of the experiment [19], is, however, systematically depicted by different systems, independently of the size of the vesicle and of its chemical composition (see Fig. 1, bottom). Hybrid bending-dilational modes could provide a plausible scenario for explaining the enhanced amplitude of the curvature modes observed at high q 's. Hybrid modes are indeed expected to become dominant at $q_C \approx (h\varepsilon/R\kappa)^{1/2}$; for POPC vesicles (sized $R \approx 20\mu$ m, $h \approx 2$ nm; elastic parameters: $\kappa \approx 10k_B T$, $\varepsilon \approx 0.09$ N/m) one gets $q_C \approx 5\mu$ m $^{-1}$; thus, a crossover regime is expected at the experimental spectral range. For stiffer membranes dominant hybrid behavior is expected even at lower q 's.

A complementary piece of evidence on the presence of hybrid modes arises from the detailed analysis of the relaxation dynamics of the curvature fluctuations, as provided from the time autocorrelation function, $G_q(t) = \langle \zeta_q(\tau)\zeta_q(\tau+t) \rangle \sim \langle \zeta_q^2 \rangle \exp(-\Gamma t)$. Figure 2 (top) shows the experimental autocorrelation functions obtained for the first fluctuation modes of POPC vesicles. Although the sequences of the vesicle fluctuations lapse 30 s, the correlation functions typically decay in the first seconds. As expected, the experimental $G_q(t)$ follows near-exponential behavior, with relaxation rates strongly increasing with q . As explained above, pure bending fluctuations relax at a rate $\Gamma_{\text{bend}} \approx \kappa q^3/4\eta$. For POPC vesicles, $\kappa \approx 10k_B T$; thus, although the fundamental bending mode ($q = 1/R = 5 \times 10^5$ m $^{-1}$) might relax at times $\Gamma_{\text{bend}}^{-1} \approx 30$ s, longer than the experimental window, higher modes might do, however, within the experimental probed time (see dashed line in Fig. 2; bottom). Because the studied correlation functions correspond to low- q modes, the observed relaxation could be dominated by capillary effects, i.e., $\Gamma_{\text{cap}} = \gamma q/4\eta$. For POPC vesicles, we obtained $\gamma = 10^{-8}$ N/m (from fittings to the static spectra); thus, the relaxation of γ -driven modes must be observed at rates similar than the pure bending ones (see Fig. 2; bottom; dotted line). The observed dynamics is, however, rather compatible with faster hybrid modes relaxing as $\Gamma_{\text{hyb}} = \varepsilon q^2/2b$: (a) the increasing trend of the experimental rates is clearly $\sim q^2$ (neither $\sim q^1$ nor $\sim q^3$, typical of surface tension and bending modes, respectively (see Fig. 2; bottom)); and (b) the calculated friction coefficient, $b = 2 \times 10^9$ N s/m 3 , takes a reasonable value compatible with the previous estimations from experiments on flickering spectroscopy [23], tether pulling [24], and lateral diffusion of fluorescent probes [25]. Similar behavior was found by Méléard et al. from the correlation functions of the undulation modes of vesicles made of egg-yolk lecithin [26]; data follow the $\Gamma_{\text{hyb}} \sim q^2$ dependence typical of the intermonolayer frictional mechanism of the hybrid modes, taking absolute values also compatible with a friction coefficient

ca. $b \approx 10^9$ N s/m³ but not with a pure bending mechanism (see inset in Fig. 2; bottom).

From the above evidences, we deduce the presence of hybrid curvature-dilation modes as an effective class of bending motion at high q 's and short times. The presence of hybrid frictional modes has been previously argued by Pott and Méléard for explaining the anomalous relaxation dynamics of SOPC vesicles (somewhat fluid as POPC) [23]. Because the shell topology couples linearly curvature fluctuations and dilations, consequently $\delta\zeta = R\delta\rho$ [9]. In such a case, a linear expansion of the curvature fluctuations is possible with the form $\zeta_q(\rho_q) \approx \zeta_q(\rho_q = 0) + (\partial\zeta/\partial\rho)\rho_q$, where $\zeta_q(\rho_q = 0) = \zeta_q^{(0)}$ represents a pure bending fluctuation, as those considered in Eq. (1). Therefore, the time-averaged square amplitudes of the curvature fluctuations might contain two well differentiated terms; neglecting pure dilations:

$$\langle \zeta_q \zeta_q \rangle \approx \langle \zeta_q^{(0)} \zeta_q^{(0)} \rangle + 2 \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \rho} \langle \zeta_q^{(0)} \rho_q \rangle \quad (2)$$

where the first term accounts for the pure bending fluctuations of Eq. (1) and the second one $\langle \zeta_q \rho_q \rangle$ for the hybrid modes of the Seifert theory [15]. For a near-spherical vesicle, $(\partial\zeta/\partial\rho) = R$ [9]; thus the spectrum of the whole curvature fluctuations might be rewritten as follows:

$$P(q) = \frac{k_B T}{\gamma q^2 + \kappa q^4} + 12 \left(\frac{R}{h} \right) \frac{k_B T}{\varepsilon q^2} \quad (3)$$

This bimodal spectrum contains, in addition to the usual Helfrich (pure bending) term, a new contribution arising from hybrid modes, which becomes increasingly influential for larger vesicles ($\sim R/h$). After integration over the equatorial plane, the hybrid component to the bimodal spectrum in Eq. (3) takes the dependence, $P_{\text{hyb}}(q_x) \approx 12(R/h)(k_B T/\varepsilon q_x) \sim q_x^{-1}$, much weaker than pure bending modes $P_{\text{bend}}(q_x) \sim q_x^{-3}$, in agreement with the experimental observation (an exhaustive discussion has been supplied as auxiliary material [21]). Figure 3 shows representative experimental spectra obtained for two well different systems (floppy vesicles of POPC and rigid ones, with 30% added cholesterol). Predictions from the bimodal spectrum (Eq. 3) are compared with fittings of the experimental spectra to the Helfrich relationship, considering in both cases corrections explained in Ref. [19]. The relative weight of the hybrid mode is imposed by the ratio R/h , where R is fixed at the observed vesicle radius R and $h = 2$ nm[6, 18]. The spectra are then computed for typical values of γ and κ , taking typical values of the dilational elasticity obtained from rheological experiments [18]. In general, the bimodal relationship in Eq. (3) is successful in predicting the adequate spectral shape, not only its initial decay, essentially pure bending, but also the high- q tail accounting for enhanced curvature fluctuations driven by hybrid modes. In experiments, the terminal tail is systematically found higher for larger vesicles (see right panels in Fig. 3) doing this regime worthless for fitting to the usual Helfrich spectrum. Noticeably, the bimodal spectrum in Eq. (3) accounts properly for this feature

through of the R/h dependence of the hybrid contribution. In other words, the presence of hybrid modes (with amplitude $\delta\zeta = R\delta\rho$) explains the fact that larger vesicles are more efficient in creating hybrid curvature fluctuations.

To summarize, the present results embody a conclusive piece of evidence on the existence of the hybrid modes as an effective mode of curvature motion in bilayer vesicles. Consequently, the bimodal spectrum deduced in this work might be checked as an adequate extension of the Helfrich spectrum for describing undulation dynamics of lipid vesicles. Bending and dilational parameters can be simultaneously obtained from the adequate analysis of the fluctuation spectra.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported under Grants FIS2006-01305, Consolider-Ingenio in Nanociencia Molecular CSD20070010 (MICINN), and MAT/05/0283 (CAM). R. R. G. and L. R. A. thank MICINN and CAM for FPI grants. L. H. M. was supported from CSD2007-0010. I. L. M. acknowledges Juan de la Cierva program.

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[22] In a sphere, undulations larger than the equatorial contour are forbidden, thus $q_x^{(1)} = 1/R$ represents the lower cutoff for the fluctuation spectrum.

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FIG. 1. (Top) Experimental spectrum of the equatorial fluctuations of a POPC vesicle ($R = 10\mu$ m) at 22°C . The resolution limit of the undulation amplitude is ca. 10^{-22} m^3 . The straight line represents the best fit to Eq. (1) following the procedure for data reduction described in Ref. [19]. (Bottom) Experimental fluctuation spectra obtained for different vesicles with increasing amounts of cholesterol (% weight).

FIG. 2. (Top) Experimental correlation functions $G_q(t)$ for the first Fourier modes of undulation; $q_x^{(n)} = n/R$. (Bottom) Relaxation rates of the fluctuation modes Γ as obtained from the linear slopes of the $\ln G_q(t)$ vs t plots. The lines represent predictions for: (dashed lines) pure bending modes with $\kappa = 10k_B T$; (dotted lines) pure capillary modes with $\gamma \approx 10^{-8}$ J/m²; (solid lines) hybrid dilational-curvature modes with $b = 2 \times 10^9$ N/sm³. For comparison purposes experimental data of Ref. [26] have been reproduced in the inset (lines: as in the main figure).

FIG. 3. Experimental spectra of the equatorial fluctuations of POPC vesicles (top) and with 30% added cholesterol (bottom). For every system vesicles with different radii are checked; arrows mark the terminal fluctuation level at the high- q tails, which is strongly dependent on R . The straight lines represent simulated spectra from the Helfrich's theory for pure bending modes (dashed lines) and the bimodal expression in Eq. (3) (solid lines) (parameters: for POPC: $\gamma = 10^{-8} \text{ J/m}^2$, $\kappa = 10k_B T$ and $\varepsilon = 80 \text{ mN/m}$; for POPC with 30% cholesterol: $\gamma = 10^{-8} \text{ J/m}^3$, $\kappa = 30k_B T$, and $\varepsilon = 100 \text{ mN/m}$).